

Education for Sustainable Development in Nigeria: Exploring the Effects of Academic Corruption

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ABSTRACT

Achieving growth is one major striving of societies across the globe, especially the kind of growth that creates a robust economy as well as promotes quality life for the populace, while utilizing consciously the finite resources in the environment. Education has been identified as a major driver of such sustainable growth, as it transfers appropriate sets of knowledge, attitudes, and values to people and equips them with the capacity to make conscious and pro-sustainability choices in their daily lives. This paper analyzes the impact of academic corruption on sustainable development in Nigeria. It is argued here that academic corruption poses an impediment to growth and development in Nigeria, and while it originates from an individual or a groups attempt to maximize benefits through illegal means, the inadequacies of the system to prevent and reduce the opportunities for corruption contribute to its prevalence. The implications of this are seen in the quality of products from Nigeria Universities and their capacity for sustainable growth and development. As noted in this paper, there is need for serious attitudinal and structural repairs in Nigeria's education system in order to establish it as a critical factor for the broader realization of sustainable development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Academic Corruption; Corruption: Development: Education: Sustainable Development

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the key aspirations of every political order is to improve on the quality of life of its people, as well as increase their socio-economic advantages. According to Galbraith (1980), no country can be said to be developed if it cannot provide its entire populace with the basic life needs such as housing, clothing, food, security, health, employment opportunities and education; and above all that, chart out plans for economic and social development. The objective of sustainable development is to produce continuous and unrelenting improvements in human well being, which manifests in the socio-economic conditions of the people, gender parity, access to healthcare, child mortality rate, life expectancy, and access to basic needs of life. According to a BBC report of 2014, countries exhibit different levels of development of which the two most important ways of measurement are examining the economy and the human development index (HDI). Economic development on the one hand, measures a countries level of wealth and how it is generated, while human development on the other hand, measures the degree of access the population has to key needs such as food, health care, safety, education,

jobs, wealth, leisure, as well as political and cultural freedom (BBC, 2014). However, while these two are important for growth and development, investments in human development have proven to be a veritable instrument for sustainable development. As noted by UNESCO (2015) human beings are the real agents that determine the quality and pace of a nation's socio-economic development beyond economic growth. The sociological fact in this is evident in the impact of human capital development in countries like the USA, Japan, Canada, Switzerland, Norway and Finland, where human capital development has affected positively the growth of science, technology, commerce, as well as social cohesion and sustainability (WEF, 2016), but in places where human development index is poor, an increase in inequality, vulnerability, exclusion, violence, unsustainable patterns of economic production and consumption and environmental degradation has been observed (UNESCO, 2015). The Finnish development policy for instance, includes a national ethos that the people are the nation's most important resources, and they have a right to a quality education; education which is designed to equip the citizenry with problem solving aptitude and the capacity to face complex global challenges (Korpela, 2014). However, in developing countries like Nigeria, even though policy makers acknowledge the critical role of a strong human resource base in complementing other investments to boost productivity and economic growth, very insignificant efforts are put into ensuring quality education and skill development. According to Bennet (2001) and Taylor (2012), the challenges of human capital development in poor and developing countries, especially for sustainability, are profound and complex, ranging from insignificant investments in education to the phenomenon of corruption, causing them to record low averages in educational attainments. These observations therefore make it imperative to carefully explore how corruption in Nigeria's education system impacts sustainable development,

L.1 The problem

Education in particular has been singled out as a fundamental tool for socio-economic development; as nations that have recorded remarkable accomplishments across the globe today are seen to have relied heavily on information, technology, and the instrumentations of education. The quality of knowledge generated within educational institutions and its availability to the wider economy is critical to national competitiveness and growth. In the light of this, Ajayi & Afolabi (2009), posits that education remains a heuristic device which will not only assist in meeting a nation's social, political, cultural and economic goals, but will also arm its citizenry with required knowledge, dexterity, character and desirable values that will foster National development. Nigeria, by all reckoning, should be one of the most developed countries of the world considering the abundance of natural and human resources the country is endowed with. In the 70's, Nigeria was one of the 50 richest countries in the world but has, at the threshold of the twenty first century, retrogressed to become one of the 25 poorest countries in the world ((Kaura, 2011; Igbuzor, 2013). Nigeria, for Igbuzor (2013), presents paradox in terms of development as it is the 6th largest exporter of Oil, with a robust GDP, and at the same time hosts the 3 largest number of poor people in the world; after China and India. Various explanations have been adduced for this frightening situation, one of which is an outstanding theory a defective educational system. According to the 2004 National Economic empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) Assessment Report, Nigeria's development challenges are largely an outcome of poor development plans, low per capita

growth, unsustainable public sector spending, domestic debt, low productivity, over reliance on Oil while neglecting other productive sectors, and above all a dysfunctional education system. As Okecha (2009) and Ilechukwu, Njoku & Ugwuozor (2014), had noted, Nigeria's education system is bedeviled with a multitude of problems, and the situation is worsening day by day as challenges such as poor funding, low staff-student ratio, acute shortage of infrastructure and facilities, inconsistent and ill-conceived policies, unstable curriculum, exam malpractices and corruption at high and low places, etc, has inhibited quality and fitness of purpose in human development forcing Nigeria's educational system into a ridiculous state. The sociological implication of this is that human capital is negatively affected; a situation which also triggers a barrage of social problems such as unemployment, poor productivity, poverty, crime, violence and conflict as experienced in Nigeria today. Already, statistics reveal that unemployment rate in Nigeria has increased from 10.4% in the fourth quarter of 2015 to 14.2% in the first quarter of 2017, while poverty rate is 67.1% (n=112 million) of the country's 167 million people and crime rate, an alarming 64.65% (Ahiuma-Young, 2016; Trading economics, 2017; NUMBEO, 2017; Olawoyin, 2017), The relationship between these statistics and the intractable challenge of human development in the country may be arguable, but as WEF (2016), Onuba(2016) and Christian (2016), had argued, all of these contribute to the debilitating underdevelopment challenges bedeviling the country. The problematic of this paper identify factors related to academic corruption that impede education for sustainable development in Nigeria and to examine how academic corruption deteriorate the competencies of graduates of tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. The role of in Sustainable Development

Education, like health, is often seen as an unproblematic social good to which everyone is entitled as a right. Governments everywhere in the world have assumed a considerable role in educating their citizens, this is primarily because education is considered a fundamental human right and essential for the exercise of all other human rights (UNESCO, 2015). Education here refers to the purposive, conscious or unconscious, psychological, sociological, scientific and philosophical processes that bring about the development of the individual to the fullest extent and the maximum development of the society through learning in such a way that both enjoy maximum happiness and prosperity. Although clear gains have been recorded in education across globe; emphasis now is on quality education as a driver for sustainable development. & Didham (2014) noted that the prior focus of education was on access and attainment as embodied in the Education for All (EFA) and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs); the concern for many countries now is quality education for sustainable development (ESD). That is a shift from ordinary impartation of knowledge to fitness of purpose viz-a-viz; institutional vision, levels of achievement, excellence and outcomes that encompass knowledge, skills and attitudes that are linked to national goals for education and positive participation in society which are components of quality education (UNICEF, 2000; Williams, 2011), Manrique- Gil & Claros (2000) had posited that access to quality education is essential for development; it is the foundation for a country's sustainable growth in its economic, social and environmental dimensions. In 2000, The World Education Forum (WEF) organized by UNESCO, mobilized the national community around a shared development agenda in

education; thereafter 164 countries committed themselves to meet the goal of quality education for all by 2015 (UNESCO, 2011). Likewise in 2013, the EU organized a high level conference on education to debate ongoing challenges and to ensure that education play a prominent role in the post-2015 development Mamework (Manrique-Gil and Claros, 2000). According to UNESCO (2009), as cited in Ofci- Manu and Didham (2014), a holistic approach to quality education provides capabilities to address numerous global sustainability crises such as gender inequality, poverty, insecurity and environmental degradation. For Ofei-Manu and Didham (2014), there are typically two distinct pedagogical interpretations of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD); the first is ESD as a means to transfer appropriate sets of knowledge, attitudes, and values to the learner. The second is to equip people with the needed capacity to make conscious, pro-sustainability choices in their daily lives and to cooperatively explore these issues through collective discourse as a means to transform mind-sets and lifestyles. All of these show the well warranted global enthusiasm for promoting education, especially as a tool for socio-economic advancement and sustainability.

Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Sustainability is about improving the quality of life for everyone while ensuring that we do not detract from future generations the capacity for sustenance. The essence of this form of development is to fashion a stable relationship between human activities and the natural environment which ensures that development today does not diminish the prospects for future generations to enjoy a quality of life at least as good as our own (Mondal, 2016). Education has been identified as an integral element of and a key enabler for sustainable development Education for sustainable development aims to ensure that learning enables people to make responsible decisions that guarantee the best outcome for our fragile world, particularly in the proper management of means and resources

2.1.2. Academic corruption, Sustainability and the challenge of Quality Education in Nigeria

With the definition and emphasis of development moving away from solely economic growth to a larger outlook that includes the three pillars of sustainability - environmental, economic and social, and the recognition that policy instruments and technological solutions are not going to be enough, behavioral change, through education, has become critical to achieving sustainable development (CEE, 2016). For Ofei-Manu and Didham (2014) education now aims at arming people with competencies essential to addressing issues of sustainability. When sustainability becomes the central issue in higher education, education programmes focus on sustainability components which include building student capacity to fully understand and manage sustainability challenges. These Sustainability competencies (SC) prepare learners to be systemic problem solvers, change agents, and transition managers (Wick, Withycombe, and Redman, 2011; Ofei-Manu and Didham, 2014). As noted by Wiek, Withycombe, and Redman (2011), sustainability competencies provided by quality education includes systems-thinking competence which is the ability to analyze complex systems across different fields (environment, society, economy, etc.) and scales (local to global) while considering systemic features and frameworks; anticipatory competence which is the ability to analyze, evaluate, and

articulate the long-term future of various sustainability issues, including unintended consequences and inter-generational equity; the ability to convey, apply, and negotiate sustainability values, goals, and targets which is regarded as normative competence; strategic competence which entails the ability to "get things done" by designing and implementing interventions and transformative strategies toward improved sustainability and interpersonal competence, which involves the ability to motivate, enable, and facilitate collaborative and participatory sustainability research and problem solving. For Van Kerkhoff and Lebel (2006) these five competencies must be integrated to successfully co-create knowledge and action for sustainability. Figure 1 provides a framework showing the functional links among the five key competencies for sustainable development.

Figure 1: Sustainability research and problem-solving framework with key sustainability competencies. Source: Wiek, Withycombe, & Redman (2011).

Furthermore, Bloom, Canning and Chan (2006) had argued that apart from the general implications of education on development, education can also have direct benefits for economies. For instance, by producing well-trained teachers, it can enhance the quality of primary and secondary education systems and give secondary graduates greater opportunities for economic advancement; by training physicians and other health workers, it can improve a society's health, and by nurturing governance and leadership skills, it can provide countries with the talented individuals needed to establish a policy environment favorable to growth while setting up robust and fair legal and political institutions, creating a culture of job and entrepreneurship, addressing environmental problems and improving security against internal and external threats. Bloom, Canning and Chan (2006), using the flow chart below also posited that higher education benefits economies in a lot of ways. For Bloom, Canning and Chan (2006) education increases the chances and the benefits of research and development, entrepreneurship, commerce and productivity, governance, safety, tolerance, and effective management of means and resources.

Figure 2: Quality education and Development(Bloom, Canning and Chan, 2006).

Further empirical surveys on the gains of education have also revealed that education is one of the keys to unlocking a country's potential for economic growth. For instance; wages, agricultural income and productivity are higher where persons involved receive better education (UNESCO. 2011). Again, globalization and international trade requires countries and their economies to compete with each other, and the economically successful countries will definitely hold competitive and comparative advantage over other economies. To achieve this, countries send so have various industries in the global marketplace, and these industries will be managed by a capable workforce. Hence the need to build a strong education system that will produce workers able to function in productive industries (Radcliffe & Walther, 2015). From a global perspective, economic development are increasingly driven by the advancement and application of knowledge (Saint, Hartnett & Strassner, 2003). Besides the economy, education also affects other social aspects of a country's development in areas such as health, social justice, peace and general life satisfaction (Hanushek, 2005; UNESCO, 2015; GPE, 2015). Burchi & DeMuro (2007) argued that education is both theoretically and empirically proven to promote development especially in terms of fighting food insecurity. In their work, it was demonstrated that an increase of children's school attendance rate by 100% can reduce food insecurity by approximately 19%. This new perspective opines that the contribution of an enhanced society goes beyond the economic growth of a country, and does affect positively the life of people. especially that of the least advantaged.

Although Nigeria, like many other sub-Saharan African countries, has invested in providing education for her citizenry, and has made considerable progress in achieving mass literacy, the country with a population of over 180 million people and an abundant natural resource, still remains one of Africa's most impoverished countries, as its people endure a deplorable situation of poverty, unemployment, inequality, insecurity and environmental pollution (Saint,et al, 2003; WPR, 2014). The socio-economic conditions in Nigeria presents a perplexing paradox, for inspite of a robust endowment in human and natural resources, the level of poverty and the infrastructural decadence stand in contrast to the country's enormous wealth. As noted by Omoh (2014) and FDI (2015), Nigeria today ranks third on world poverty index, with over

70% of her population living below \$1.25 or even less per day. Nigerians live under very terrible conditions, from awful roads and rails, to poor irrigation systems and water pipelines, to poor mobile and broadband networks, housing, and energy which its supply is desperately inadequate (Omoh, 2004, FDI, 2015). Infrastructures are weak, and this exerts a huge burden on foreign and local business which in turn hampers job creation and poverty alleviation. This explains why unemployment in the country is alarming. According to the National Bureau of statistics (2014), more than 17,7 million people of the labour force population are either unemployed or underemployed. Education which should create greater tax revenue, increase savings and investment, and lead to a more entrepreneurial and civic society, improve a nation's health, contribute to reduced population growth, improve technology, and strengthen governance. years to be ineffective in Nigeria, as many of its products have been accused of not to being able to defend their grades or perform effectively when employed in the corporate and craft industry. A few years ago a UNESCO report noted that Nigeria's educational system is unemployable illiterates who lack the critical human and analytical tools to connect, compete and collaborate in an increased globalised work environment (Ada, 2004; Ojeifo, 2015). This situation shows the presence of a systemic problem that requires urgent attention if Nigeria is going to join the rest of the world as a viable economy in years to come. Kofi Annan, who served as the 7th secretary general of the UN, stressed that the university must become a primary tool for Africa's development in the new century. Universities can help develop African expertise; they can enhance the analysis of African problems; strengthen domestic institutions; serve as a model environment for the practice of good governance, conflict resolution and respect for human rights, and enable African academics to play an active part in the global community of scholars (UNIS, 2000). How Nigeria can effectively harness the prospects of quality education as a primary tool for development remains uncertain in the face of the dwindling educational standards in the country. According to the 11th UNESCO EFA report. Nigeria's education sector faces such a bleak future in the face of numerous infrastructural and systemic problems, including lack of infrastructure and deprived manpower to adequately cater for the demand for education. Premised on these UNESCO has projected that it will take Nigeria about 70 years before all children will have access to primary education, as presently there are over 10 million out of school children in Nigeria and more than 40 million illiterate adults (Abayomi & Arenyeka, 2014).

According to Okemakinde (2014) three pieces of evidence suggests the need for urgent attention in education especially in curricula and pedagogy. First is the high dropout rate in universities, second is the inadequate competency in university graduates and thirdly the lack of quality and fitness purpose in tertiary institutions curricula. Okemakinde (2014) noted that the factors responsible for poor quality of education in Nigeria tertiary institutions are both internal and external, Internal factors include strikes, lack of employee's motivation, and a weak accountability for educational performance. External factors comprises of teachers' shortages. inconsistent government funding, admissions based on quota system rather than merit, and the phenomenon of corruption. Professor Ayo Bamgbose in his paper "Academic corruption and the role of the Nigerian National Order of Merit in curbing to the 2015 annual forum of the Nigerian National Order of Merit (NNOM) in Abuja, argued that academic corruption is foremost culprit eroding the standards of education in Nigeria. He pointed at practices such as

absenteeism, negligence of duty, demand for gratifications in exchange for grades, post graduate research plagiarism and other examination malpractices, as some of the cardinal sins of corruption that destroy Nigeria's education system (Rufai, 2016). While in the public domain corruption is the improbity or decay in the decision-making process in which a decision maker consent to deviate or demands deviation from criterion which should his or her decision making, in exchange for a reward or for the promise or expectation of a reward, academic corruption here refers to all forms of deviation from justice, honesty, fairness, probity, impartiality and discipline expected from institutions of learning (Van Duyne, 2001; Adedimeji. 2015). For Kasovi (2014), academic corruption includes all selfish acts that are contrary to the just and equitable delivery of higher education which arises from the moral impurity of the individual(s) who deviate from the expected behaviour ideal and instead, behave in a selfish and repugnant way. Such acts includes plagiarism, fabrication, deception, cheating, bribery, sabotage, professional misconduct on the part of tutors, impersonation on the part of students or professors, the use of institutional authority or name for personal gain in the process of higher education delivery or reception. Oni (2000) and Rufai (2016) also noted that the implications of academic corruption for National development are grave; the end result is the founding of a system that cannot produce high caliber manpower that will dominate and compete globally in administration, science and technology, manufacturing, agriculture, institutional analysis, research, and trade.

2.1.3. Theoretical framework

Various explanations have been advanced to explain the causes of corruption especially in the education system. According to Eckstein (2003), academic corruption is as a result of both subjective and objective factors. Subjective factors are primarily attitudinal and individual; and include variables such as varying competitive energies of participants in academic life, simple ignorance of rules and conventions that embody what is right or unacceptable, or an individuals analysis of the benefits and costs of corruption; all of which together or singly could prompt an individual to engage in corrupt practices. Objective factors on the other hand comprises of the pressures directed at the individual by the society. For instance, emphasis on certification or a society's demand for skilled and educated workforce could prompt people to cut corners to attain these prerequisites. Inconsistencies in defining proper behaviour, vague policies on the appropriate punishment for violation, leniency and permissiveness for misdemeanor, and the deficiencies in the mechanism for detecting and dealing with infractions, and a pervasive culture of corruption are other objective factors that could influence academic corruption. Premised on this analysis, two theories, the rational choice theory and the systemic corruption theory, provided the framework for this study.

The rational-choice theory posits that crime is a purposive behaviour designed to meet the actors satisfaction following an analysis of the risks and pleasure involved. For this theory, people engage in corrupt practices because their personal cost-benefit analysis informs them that acting in a corrupt manner seems to be the most rational decision that will maximize their personal profit, especially when the hedonistic calculus indicates that the benefits of corruption outweighs its costs. The systemic corruption theory on the other hand is interested in the influence of social forces and practices on the human behaviour as regards corruption.

Corruption is said to be systemic, pervasive or entrenched, when corrupt practices, on a small or large scale, is norm and routine in dealings between the public sector and firms, or individuals in a given society (World Bank, 1997). As opposed to exploiting occasional opportunities, systemic corruption is ingrained in the norm and other essential aspects of a society's system. Systemic corruption explains the situation in which the major institutions and processes of the state are routinely dominated and used by corrupt individuals and groups, and in which most people have no alternatives than to corrupt. Factors that encourage systemic corruption include conflicting incentives for integrity and misdemeanor, discretionary powers, lack of transparency, low pay, and a culture of impunity (Alcazar and Andrade, 2001).

For this theory, the parading nature of academic corruption in Nigeria's education sector is both objective and subjective, as those who indulge in these malfeasances often do that because they feel it is the most profitable and convenient way to navigate the system. This cannot also be divorced from the fact that the system has shown limitations in reprimanding them. The implication here is that there is a greater acknowledgment that academic corruption diminishes the sustainability qualities of graduates of Nigerian educational institutions. As stated earlier, Education which should create greater tax revenue, increase savings and investment, and lead to a more entrepreneurial and civic society, improve a nation's health, contribute reduced population growth, improve technology, and strengthen governance, appears to be ineffective in Nigeria, as many of its product have been accused of not to being able to defend their grades or perform effectively when employed in the corporate and craft industry.

3. CONCLUSION

The general development of any nation depends largely on the quality of education attained by its citizenry. Therefore, the quest for any kind of development cannot be realized without a solid educational base. Manrique-Gil & Claros (2000) also argue that access to quality education is essential for development; it is the foundation for a country's sustainable growth in its economic, social and environmental dimensions. Education consequently becomes the key upon which the developmental base of a nation hinges. The educational sector produces the manpower that manages all aspects of the economy. As stated earlier, Globalization and international trade requires countries and their economies to compete with each other, and economically successful countries will definitely hold competitive and comparative advantage over other economies. This prompts countries to ensure a capable workforce that can achieve a strong comparative advantage in the global marketplace is reproduced via the educational sector. Economies that cannot produce such capacities and competencies usually find development challenging (Daluha, 2015; Manrique-Gil and Claros, 2000; Radcliffe & Walther, 2015). This study revealed that one of the major causes of the deteriorating status of education in Nigeria is academic corruption. Academic corruption also diminishes the quality and competencies of the products of Nigeria education system, and by extension sustainable development in the country. Heyneman (2009) cited in Kuranchie. Twene & Mensah (2014) posited that corruption affects three aspects of education which are access, equity and quality. Corrupt practices also have a high propensity to negatively affect the moral, emotional and social formation of the students who are affected by it. Corruption squanders the resources available to educational institutions; limit access to education and reduce quality of services

offered by the institutions (Emaikwu and Eba, 2007; Hallack & Poison, 2007). The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2015) have explained that corruption does not just steal money from where it is needed the most, it leads to weak governance; it breeds a kind of system that doesn't have the justification and strength of character to condemn or reprove misdemeanor, this in turn encourages more corruption and criminal activities in the society.

4. RECOMMENDATION

Corruption sets very bad precedents, thereby creating a culture that gradually destroys integrity, efficiency and quality in all sectors of a society, consequently impeding development. Hence, if Nigeria is to surmount its sustainable development challenges, then very significant steps need to be taken, particularly in the area of quality education. For instance the application of a well- developed curriculum and educational programs focused on building capacity for sustainability will help the country train a workforce of systemic problem solvers, change agents and transition managers. Also adequate funding of the education sector, professional development training opportunities to equip teachers with new skills and knowledge especially in the areas of Sustainable Development (ESD) and improved staff welfare are also crucial to achieving quality education and the of academic corruption. As Van Rijckegehem and Weder (2001) and Abbink (2002) had argued, when workers are underpaid, they may find themselves under pressure to supplement their income in "unofficial" ways, hence appropriate compensation and improved welfare clearly affects motivation and attitude towards corruption. It is also important to note that clear policies on what constitutes corruption, consequences of misconduct and an effective mechanism to detect misdemeanor, are key to discouraging academic corruption.

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